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INNOVATIVE DIRECTIONS OF RENEWAL OF COMPETITIVENESS OF ECONOMY

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Abstract. The authors form innovative directions of renewal of competitiveness of economy based on the analysis of the relationship between competitiveness and innovation in the countries of the world. The analysis of the European experience allows authors to determine the main criteria for the formation of an innovative economy: (1) more than 80% of GDP growth in the innovative economy is provided by the production of knowledge-intensive products; (2) the rate of growth of financing of fundamental research exceeds the rate of growth of the volume of purchases by the industry of science-intensive technologies. The authors note that the main directions of the search for economic development and increasing competitiveness in states are not attempts to partially update existing production systems, but the use of the “advancement” strategy. The main focus of the “advancement” strategy is not improvement, but the fundamental technology of innovation.

Keywords: competitiveness, innovations, the Global Innovation Index, the Global Sustainable Competitiveness Index.

Introduction. Innovative potential and its achievements largely determine the prospective competitiveness of the national economy. This creates a basis for the growth stability in conditions of market fluctuations and processes of globalization of economic relations. Innovative activity first brings the business out of balance, and then, with a favorable result, not only restores it, but moves it to a higher level, which other competing business entities have not yet reached. That is, innovations allow enterprises to gain a temporary basis, and, therefore, additional competitive advantages that can be maintained for a long time. Thus, innovative activity is the key to the sustainable development of an economic entity. Economic growth that is innovative in nature is called development.

Literature review. The paper (Csath, M., 2007) examines different views, approaches and models of economic competitiveness and its key drivers. The work also explores additional factors, especially so-called intangibles, affecting competitiveness. These factors are increasingly important in the long term, the author argues. The article is based on the results of the most widely recognized studies of competitiveness, including the yearbook of the Institute for Management Development, as well as various EU documents. Hungary is used as an example to illustrate the author's conclusions and suggestions. The most important argument is that competitiveness cannot be measured solely on the basis of short-term economic factors. Reliable results can only be achieved if not only economic but also social factors are used to measure competitiveness.

The article (Ganna Kharlamova & Olga Vertelieva, 2013) has three main objectives: defining "national competitiveness" as an economic category; analysis of factors affecting the level of national competitiveness and identification of groups of

countries according to the level of their relative national competitiveness. The data of Ukraine and 29 states that were clustered in accordance with the same stage of development on the basis of the Global Competitiveness Index during 2004-2012 were accepted for the study. Applied cluster analysis helped to solve the problem of statistical research of national competitiveness as a consequence of the classification of countries by their competitiveness taking into account national characteristics. In addition, cluster analysis allowed to test assumptions about the existence of some structures in a sample of countries.

The author of the article (Sanjaya, Lall, 2001) emphasizes that the decision-making bodies of developing countries are worried about national competitiveness and closely monitor indices assessing international competitiveness. From a development economy perspective, this article analyzes whether competitiveness is a legitimate issue and whether the leading indices deserve the attention they receive. The article evaluates the World Economic Forum's Global Competitiveness Report, and the author finds flaws at several levels. The author believes that its definitions are too broad, the approach is biased and the methodology is imperfect. Many qualitative indicators are vague, redundant or incorrect. These weak theoretical and empirical frameworks reduce the value of indices for analytical or policy purposes.

The paper (Valentina Diana Rusu & Angela Roman, 2018) analyzes the main economic factors affecting the competitiveness of Central and Eastern European countries. The study was conducted in a sample of ten countries (Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Estonia, Hungary, Lithuania, Latvia, Poland, Romania, Slovenia and Slovakia) for the period 2004-2016. These countries were grouped by economic development stages, respectively: countries with efficiency-oriented economies, efficiency-oriented economies, and innovation-oriented economies. Econometric analysis of group data was used, taking into account the country's competitiveness as

a dependent variable, quantified using the Global Competitiveness Index. The findings show important differences between countries, but also some similarities.

Taking into account the relevance of the selected topic of research and scientific achievements of scientists and practitioners of the world, the purpose of the article is to form innovative directions of renewal of competitiveness of economy based on the analysis of the relationship between competitiveness and innovation in the countries of the world.

Methodology. The following indicators are used as a methodology of this work:

- the Global Innovation Index, which is a multidimensional assessment of the national innovation sphere, which is entrusted with the task of determining the country's position on the level of innovative development in the world context\$

- the Global Sustainable Competitiveness Index, which is a comprehensive study and its accompanying ranking of countries in the world, in terms of economic competitiveness.

Main part

In a market economy, the driving force of innovative activity is competition, which forces enterprises to choose more advanced methods of development and guarantees them a favorable position on the market, its maintenance and expansion. Each economic entity defines a development strategy based on:

- the general rules of conduct established by the legislator;
- one's own interests, goals and opportunities;
- the market positions provided by competition [2; 4].

With all the variety of innovations, their main consumer is production, which in the conditions of an innovative economy should be receptive to innovations. This receptivity is possible under the following conditions:

- innovative activity becomes an indispensable condition for maintaining the competitiveness of production and obtaining additional profit by entrepreneurs;
- production has or can attract resources necessary for innovative activity;
- there is comprehensive information about the possibilities of innovative transformations and the expected effectiveness of innovative projects;
- taking into account the risks and significant duration of innovation payback, the macroeconomic policy of the state provides the necessary and sufficient preferences to stimulate the innovative activity of entrepreneurs [3; 7].

Currently, a new type of economic growth is actively forming in the world economy. Its driving force is the system of reproduction and use of knowledge created by the state and nationally oriented business and its implementation in innovation - the most significant resources of modern economic development, as well as mechanisms for their expanded reproduction and capitalization.

An indispensable condition for the functioning of the innovative economy is the integration of the innovative sphere into the market space. By itself, the commercialization of scientific results, which creates the prerequisites for the entry of the innovative sphere into the system of market relations and the formation of the financial base for its development, but without the corresponding organizational and economic transformations, cannot be carried out [5; 9].

Attempts to overcome this problem in foreign practice led to the formation of the “triple spiral” concept, the essence of which is the systematic accounting in the construction of the national innovation system of three interacting factors - the dynamics of the market, the dynamics of the macro environment, and the internal dynamics of the innovation sphere.

The definition of “national” in the literature is unambiguously interpreted as a “state” innovation system. Such a definition is fully justified, since the states of Europe are mainly formed on a national basis. However, in many countries there is an

administrative division into regions. In this case, the term “national” loses its original meaning. The following circumstances draw attention here:

- the state can apply a unified system of economic approaches, even under the conditions that the socio-economic development of some regions may differ significantly;

- in the case of significant differences in regional socio-economic development, each region also needs to adopt a separate approach, which should be formed at the national level with the participation of relevant regional authorities [1; 4].

Thus, for countries with a regional distribution, when building a national strategy for innovative development and choosing directions for their development, it is necessary to take into account both general principled approaches and individual features of the regions.

The analysis of the European experience allows us to determine the main criteria for the formation of an innovative economy:

- firstly, more than 80% of GDP growth in the innovative economy is provided by the production of knowledge-intensive products;

- secondly, the rate of growth of financing of fundamental research exceeds the rate of growth of the volume of purchases by the industry of science-intensive technologies [3; 8].

As for the general principled approaches to the formation of the national innovation strategy, it is the transformation of knowledge into the main strategic resource, and innovative activity into a determining factor in the development of the economy, as well as the idea of scientific and research potential as an institutional basis for ensuring the competitiveness of the economy.

European experience confirms that the path to the formation of a competitive economy is characterized by stages, balance, as well as the application of mechanisms of state and market regulation of the economy in a variant adapted to a

particular region. In particular, TOP-10 countries by the Global Sustainable Competitiveness Index in 2022 is shown on the Figure 1 [8].

Figure 1. TOP-10 countries by the Global Sustainable Competitiveness Index in 2022

Source: <https://solability.com/global-sustainable-competitiveness-index/global-sustainable-competitiveness-index-2022>

An extremely important role in building a competitive economy is assigned to the state in the implementation of the following functions:

- development of a strategy for the innovative development of the economy;
- creation of a favorable basis for the development of innovative business;

- organization of the process of forecasting technological development and determination of scientific and technical priorities on this basis;
- development of innovative infrastructure;
- development of measures for indirect and direct stimulation of innovations;
- direct participation in the development of research and development, mainly in the field of fundamental research. In particular, most innovative countries in 2022 by global innovation index score are shown on the Figure 2 [6].

Figure 2. Most innovative countries in 2022 by global innovation index score

Source: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1102558/most-innovative-countries-gii-score/>

From Figures 1 and 2 it can be seen that the level of competitiveness of countries is largely determined by the level of their innovative development.

Accordingly, today, it is necessary to implement such a model of the strategy of innovative development of the economy, where all resource opportunities should be focused on the innovative structure of development. Such innovative development structures are certainly the following:

- The National Academy of Sciences, which should be given the status of the main scientific and expert center of the country,
- other academies;
- science of higher education institutions;
- high-tech complex.

This will make it possible to concentrate intellectual resources on solving the strategic task of transferring the economy to an innovative path of development, and to bring the obtained scientific results to serial production and enter the domestic and foreign markets. But in order to create a truly new, competitive economy, it is necessary to ensure the synergy of the implementation of the mentioned programs with the development strategy of the sectors of the Ukrainian economy: consumer, high-tech, mineral and raw materials, fuel and energy, and infrastructure.

The above mentioned does not mean abandoning the course of scientific and technological development of the country's economy, but only corrects the principled approach to its implementation.

It is worth emphasizing that 77% of the total number of innovations is accounted for by improving innovations. Therefore, the current practice of scientific and technical progress in developed countries consists almost exclusively of innovations with a low degree of novelty.

At the same time, breakthrough, radical innovations make up only 14% of the total number of innovations. However, the returns from such innovations are disproportionately large. Together, they bring almost 30% of all profits received by Western companies from innovative activities [3; 8].

But even these numbers do not reflect the full value of radical innovation. It should not be forgotten that they are at the origin of subsequent improvements, adaptations to the interests of certain groups of consumers and other product modernizations. Without radical innovations, the entire stream of scientific and technical progress would have stopped in place or moved very slowly.

Thus, the main directions of the search for economic development and increasing competitiveness in states are not attempts to partially update existing production systems, but the use of the “advancement” strategy. The main focus of the “advancement” strategy is not improvement, but the fundamental technology of innovation.

Conclusions

In general, the research makes it possible to state that the changes in the ideology of individual private companies, which have emerged, are gradually moving from the implementation of the standard policy of “building up resources” to the policy of stimulating changes through the policy of the “learning process”. In particular, new behavioral trends in companies include:

- moving away from rigid hierarchy;
- creation of multifunctional teams with an emphasis on continuous training of personnel and development of labor potential.

More attention is also paid to the assimilation of new knowledge by their consumers.

At the same time, there are a number of unsolved problems that determine the direction of innovation policy development in the future. First of all, it is about ensuring the balanced development of the three main components of the innovative economy - the formation of new knowledge, the dissemination of knowledge and the consumption of knowledge.

Discussion

The key issues in the context of state management of economic competitiveness through innovation policy are also the following:

- growth of integration and coordination of innovation policy, also at the national and regional levels, formation of criteria for evaluating its effectiveness in various areas, improvement of the process of assimilation and expansion of knowledge in companies;
- modernization of the European social model through investment in human resources and the construction of welfare states.

References

1. CSATH, M. (2007). THE COMPETITIVENESS OF ECONOMIES: DIFFERENT VIEWS AND ARGUMENTS. *Society and Economy*, 29(1), 87–102. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/41472072>.

2. Ganna Kharlamova, Olga Vertelieva, The International Competitiveness of Countries: Economic-Mathematical Approach, *Economics & Sociology*, Vol. 6, No 2, 2013, pp. 39-52. DOI: 10.14254/2071-789X.2013/6-2/4

3. Global Competitiveness Report 2020. URL: <https://www.weforum.org/publications/the-global-competitiveness-report-2020/in-full/>

4. Ján Dvorský, Martin Čepel, Mihaela Simionescu & Pavol Ďurana. (2021) The Influence of Competitiveness on Start-up in SMES Segment. *E+M Ekonomie a Management* 24:1, pages 102-117.

5. Milja Marčeta & Štefan Bojnec. (2020) Drivers of Global Competitiveness in the European Union Countries in 2014 and 2017. *Organizacija* 53:1, pages 37-52.

6. Most innovative countries in 2022, by global innovation index score. URL: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1102558/most-innovative-countries-gii-score/>

7. Sanjaya Lall, Competitiveness Indices and Developing Countries: An Economic Evaluation of the Global Competitiveness Report, World Development, Volume 29, Issue 9, 2001, Pages 1501-1525, ISSN 0305-750X, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0305-750X\(01\)00051-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0305-750X(01)00051-1).

8. The Global Sustainable Competitiveness Index (GSCI) 2022. URL: <https://solability.com/global-sustainable-competitiveness-index/global-sustainable-competitiveness-index-2022>

9. Valentina Diana Rusu & Angela Roman (2018) An empirical analysis of factors affecting competitiveness of C.E.E. countries, Economic Research-Ekonomska Istraživanja, 31:1, 2044-2059, DOI: 10.1080/1331677X.2018.1480969.

10. World Competitiveness Ranking 2023. URL: <https://www.imd.org/centers/wcc/world-competitiveness-center/rankings/world-competitiveness-ranking/>